

METHODS OF TEACHING THE LIFE AND CREATION OF ISAJON SULTON IN OUT-OF-CLASS COURSES

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the effectiveness of organizing extracurricular activities for students studying in the school education system. It is necessary to study the life and creative activity of Isajon Sultan in depth and to use additional training in the promotion of his works. The use of Isajon Sultan's works is of great importance in the study of national values, folk traditions and unique expressions of students. There are recommendations on the use of FSMU, retelling, additional questions and answers in the organization of training sessions.

KEY WORDS: Method of organizing additional classes, artistic analysis, expressive reading, FSMU, reanalysis, modern technological tools, idea of the work.

INTRODUCTION.

According to modern pedagogical approaches, in the educational process it is very important to familiarize students with various characteristic works and creative activities of creators that are not included in the textbook system. In this regard, measures for the organization of extracurricular activities, their management and evaluation procedures are organized on the basis of model lessons or non-traditional methods. In the traditional lesson system, the study hours of the life and creativity of artists are conducted on the basis of one or two hours. It is appropriate to choose the life and work of Isajon Sultan for high school students. The reason for this is the existence of high-quality works of Isajon Sultan's works in the language of the shield, the style of artistic depiction, a small number of heroes and characters. His works such as "Fate", "Something happened to my father", "Mother", "Friend" are of great importance in the circles of exemplary literature. The reason why these works are chosen as the main topic of extra classes is their high effectiveness in deepening the psychological changes of high school students and their outlook on life. This is the main factor of the modern literature teaching system.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

Expression of opinion within the framework of the topic, analysis of the idea of the work, sharing of life experiences in relation to the given style of image also occurs on the basis of speech and professional competence. Both types of speech form are developed in the expression of thoughts related to the topic. It is necessary to answer the questions asked by the teacher or comment on the problem situation according to the FSMU method. The idea that led to the solution, the reason to prove that the idea is correct and clear, helps a lot to explain the form of literary approach. Also, in the process of analyzing Isajon Sultan's works, creating conflicting situations in relation to examples and examples also creates characteristic features in the student's personality. Also, the promotion of modern computer technologies in literature classes creates the relevance of the topic. In this case, electronic textbooks,

electronic libraries, and the electronic conduct of educational methodological works are also specified in the software. "In the application of information and communication technologies to the educational process in the differentiated education of students, the following tasks are required:

- it is necessary to create additional electronic reserves, data and libraries, develop special software that provides information search on the network;
- improving the educational and methodological work of teachers, establishing cooperation with experts in the fields of Internet use, information technologies and psychology;
- use of information on the latest advances in science and technology;
- use of advanced pedagogical technologies and active methods in computer-assisted teaching;
- paying special attention to students' activity and ability to work independently in the assessment".[1]

RESULTS.

Analyzing the works according to the age characteristics of schoolchildren, explaining the meaning of literary details and sentences in order to increase the level of understanding of the ideas and content presented in the works creates a unique task. Also, objections have been expressed regarding the order of how much of the sample lesson hours to teach Isajon Sultan's work should be devoted to his life activities and how many to his creative activities. The issues of evaluating and encouraging students who actively participated in additional training were also analyzed. "When setting a problem that creates a problematic situation, the following conditions are followed: 1. The problematic task should rely on the previously formed knowledge, skills and abilities of the students. Pupils should be able to understand the conditions of the assignment and come to its solution independently as a result of diligent efforts to complete it. The problem should include one unknown issue (paths, conditions or attitude) that the student will need to determine during its solution".[2]

DISCUSSION

Normative forms of evaluation programs of modern methodological methods play a big role in the organization of extracurricular literature circles and the teaching of literature representatives such as Isajon Sultan, Shukur Kholmirezayev, Normurod Norqabilov. In the teaching of Isajon Sultan's work "Friend", methods and methods should be chosen based on real life examples and the depiction of the concepts of friendship in the foreground. The FSMU method comes in handy when teaching the "Friend" story.

- F- thought,
- S-cause,
- M-example,
- U-generalization.

Using the retelling method in teaching the life and work of Isajon Sultan in extracurricular activities is highly effective. In the process of analysis of the works "Something happened to my father", "Fate", the method of retelling is also carried out by applying methods related to educational education. This eas is also distinguished by the fact that it is aimed at providing evidence for the proposed idea and opinion, and explaining the opz opinion. The history of the creation of the work, the figurative analysis of the characters and characters involved in it is a clear proof of this. "In the process of setting requirements, it is necessary to establish control over students' compliance with them. Monitoring is done using various conditions, such as keeping a behavior log, keeping track of classroom

attendance, etc. Control should be real and regular. Students should be informed about its results. Organization and gendering of the team. It is closely related to the education of activists" [3]

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, it can be said that the organization of extracurricular activities greatly helps young students to acquire additional information and knowledge. It is very important to organize literary circles and to teach the lives of artists active in the literary process such as Shukur Kholmirezayev, Normurod Norqabilov, Isajon Sultan. Also, in the teaching of Isajon Sultan's works, one can witness the expression of national values and folk traditions in a unique way. In this, students are divided into groups or given exercises for individual development, and mutual methods and methods are used. level also plays a big role. It is necessary to organize the additional classes and their assessment technologies using modern pedagogical tools and international experiences. It is necessary to create a methodological form of studying the processes of evaluating students based on traditional and non-traditional educational systems. In this regard, it is necessary to analyze his works, to express a reaction to them, to take into account the main idea, the main image and composition of the work, whether it is compatible with the student's age range, mastery characteristics.

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